

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ КОНЦЕПЦИИ ЦИФРОВЫХ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ РЕСУРСОВ В КАЗАХСТАНЕ

Сембаева Ж.К.

*Магистрант Казахского университета международных отношений и мировых языков имени Абылай хана
Казахстан, г. Алматы*

THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE CONCEPT OF DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES IN KAZAKHSTAN

Sembayeva Zh.

*Master's student at Abylai Khan Kazakh University
of International Relations and World Languages
Kazakhstan, Almaty*

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассматриваются определения и взгляды авторов из стран СНГ и зарубежья на понятие цифровых образовательных ресурсов и их применение. Показано, как с развитием технологий и появлением других терминов это понятие приобрело свое собственное комплексное значение, которое отличается от цифрового контента, или просто цифровых технологий, или просто цифровых ресурсов. Раскрыты требования к разработке цифровых образовательных ресурсов, причем содержание самих ресурсов предлагается использовать с учетом этапа их использования, так как ЦОР в большинстве своем служат не заменой учебного процесса, а просто дополнительным инструментом в достижении образовательных целей. В данной статье перечислены некоторые наиболее известные и распространенные в Казахстане образовательные ресурсы, освещены принципы их работы и предлагаемые ими услуги.

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the definitions and perspectives of CIS and international authors on the concept of digital educational resources and their application. It demonstrates how with the development of technology and the emergence of other terms, this concept has acquired its own comprehensive meaning, which differs from digital content, or just digital technology or simply digital resources. The requirements for the development of digital learning resources have been disclosed, moreover the content of the resources itself is proposed to use taking into account the stage of their use, as DER in most serve not as a substitute for the educational process, but simply an additional tool in achieving educational goals. This paper lists some of the most well-known and widespread educational resources in Kazakhstan and highlights the way they work and the services they offer.

Ключевые слова: цифровые образовательные ресурсы, технология, цифровой контент, образовательные платформы.

Keywords: digital educational resources, technology, digital content, educational platforms.

The XXI century is considered the age of information technology and the process of its implementation in education is increasingly demanding the requirements for the quality of graduates' knowledge. Extensively, digital educational resources are used to develop digital content for students. The concept of digital educational resources is considered in the studies of a variety of authors from different points of view. First of all, let us consider the works of earlier scholars, who defined DER. Although the term began to be widely used only after the spread of digital technology and before that there were other concepts with similar notions. For instance, in the early 1990s, the term "multimedia educational resources" was used to encompass electronic materials combining text, sound, graphics and video for learning and knowledge sharing (McKenna & Fitzpatrick, 1994). These could be CD-ROMs with interactive textbooks or programs created for learning on computers. That is, it corresponded to the technological progress of that time.

In the late 20th century, the terms "computer-based educational programs" or "e-learning programs" were also used to refer to software designed to teach students on computers. These programs could include interactive exercises, tests, instructional materials, and other learning tools (Clark, 1985).

By early 2000, the concept of DER had become increasingly broad, but still at that time the definitions were not particularly distinguishable from digital content, electronic technology, and electronic materials, that is, these concepts were not very different from each other, the distinctions were more blurred. For example, according to Casey (2008), digital educational resources are defined as electronic materials used in the educational process. They include computer programs, multimedia materials, interactive textbooks, and other electronic resources that can be used to teach, share information, and support student learning activities. Or as another example, the study of Selvan and Mishra

(2006) can be cited. According to them, digital educational resources are information and communication technology (ICT)-based tools that are used in an educational environment. They include computer programs, online resources, multimedia materials and other tools designed for learning and knowledge transfer. One of the Russian authors who gave the definition of DER is Grigoriev S.G. In his opinion, DER is any information of an educational nature stored on digital media. So, these definitions demonstrate clearly that the concept of DER is imprecise and generalized, and does not contain clear boundaries with other concepts of a digital or electronic nature. More complete definitions can be found in the works of authors in the last 10 years. For example, according to Juan and Coleman (2020), digital learning resources are online platforms that provide access to a variety of learning materials, including electronic textbooks, video lectures, interactive assignments, and feedback from teachers. These resources allow students to learn anytime, anywhere, using computers, tablets, or smartphones. The authors are also very explicit in describing the challenges and consequences of DER use for teachers and educational institutions alike. Also, questions about assessment and quality of learning are raised. Yet, DER in the educational process is used more as a supporting tool than a substitute for the whole process of interaction between teachers and students. Among the Kazakh scientists engaged in the study are such authors as G.K. Nurgalieva, D.M. Jusubalieva, E.V. Artykbaeva, A.T. Chaklikova and others. Nurgalieva G.K. defines DER as applied didactic materials in digital format, which are developed on the topics of a particular subject in accordance with the curricula of the states. In this article the definition of DER will be based on this definition, as it fully discloses and distinguishes DER from other concepts of a digital nature. In 2011, DER in Kazakhstan was developed by the National Centre of Informatization, which consisted of a sound presentation, tests, interactive tasks and texts.

One of the goals of modern education is the independent learning and development of students, which is achieved by mastering the proper use of technology and digital resources. Since DER allows access to educational materials from any location and at any time, it fulfills this task perfectly.

Due to this kind of responsibility there are several requirements for the content of digital educational resources.

- Compliance with the content of the educational program and regulations of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan.
- To have interactive, multimedia and informative character.
 - Be differentiated by age, level of education, take into account cultural experiences and other characteristics of students.
 - Aim at the ability of students to solve real-life situational problems and gain experience in problem solving, in professional training solutions.
 - Build students' ability to work individually and collaboratively with groups.

- Use valid sources of information in the development of digital resources
- Have an understandable and user-friendly interface so that students can not only easily find what they need, but also avoid wasting time learning how to use the resource.

In other words, taking into account all the above, the following definition should be identified: digital educational resource is a digital collection of didactic materials often on a particular discipline, which corresponds to the topics of the educational program aimed at the formation of certain competencies in students.

The content of digital educational resources can be divided according to the order of use of certain materials during the learning process.

The first block is called the block of introduction, that is, using this block of provided materials developed on a particular topic, students receive information by reading texts, articles, illustrations, video, audio or presentations.

The next block is a block of comprehension. At this stage of work with information the student begins to reflect on the knowledge he or she has acquired - comparing it with known data, analyzing and structuring it. He or she makes connections between the new information and past experience.

The next block is called Application. It is not enough to simply memorize information, in the study of certain material the main thing is the ability to apply them in ordinary and unusual situations. the ability to manipulate the acquired information.

And the last block is a block of creativity. As it is clear from the name it is not only the application of information, but also the ability to modify it and create something new and further improve it.

One of the tasks of using DER is to teach how to navigate the flow of information, think critically, collect, synthesize, analyze and select the most appropriate for your decision and achieve your goals. Going through all the steps, or blocks, will help to achieve these results.

Kazakhstan uses a variety of digital resources in different areas. For example, Khan Academy is an educational resource where assignments and materials are created by experts in their fields, such as math, science, economics and finance, arts and humanities, and computer science. It can also help teachers identify weaknesses and personal preferences of their students and adapt their teaching to them. (<https://ru.khanacademy.org/>)

Another highly sought-after resource that many schools also use is Daryn Onlatsn, the materials of which have been created in accordance with the SOSE. In this resource, you may not only find useful, educational information, but also choose universities, take practice tests on observation tests, find a tutor, and participate in olympiads. And for teachers there are publications of articles, teaching online, getting certificates and preparation for professional development. All these features make Daryn one of the largest resources in Kazakhstan. Although it is considered as a digital educational platform or a platform for distance learning, it is as close as possible to the essence of DER compared to

other resources or platforms used in our educational institutions. (<https://daryn.online/>)

Another digital platform of educational content widely used in schools is Bilim Media Group or also called BilimLand, which includes materials developed according to the educational program up to grade 11 divided by subjects and for practical application of knowledge. Students can watch video resources and try working in a virtual laboratory, prepare for national testing and take courses based on international standards. The same for teachers have an example of how to build a resource with all the stages of the course. (<https://bilimland.kz/kk>)

Paying attention to the above material it is possible to notice rather extensive opportunities which DER provides in the modern educational environment. These include creating a more flexible and individualized learning environment where students can study at their own pace and according to their own needs. They can provide access to education for a wide range of learners, including those who are in remote areas or have limited educational opportunities. DERs also facilitate the development of information literacy skills and the use of technology, which are important in today's information society.

However, the development of DER also faces a number of challenges. These challenges include the need to constantly update and refresh content, to ensure accessibility and compatibility with different platforms and devices, and to ensure students' data security and privacy. Also, in order to realize the full potential of DER, various factors must be considered. First of all, learners and teachers need to be prepared to use digital learning resources and have the necessary skills and competencies. Effective infrastructure, including access to a reliable Internet connection and appropriate equipment, is also required.

In conclusion, digital learning resources are powerful tools that have the potential to transform education and enhance learning. They offer opportunities for

individualization, interactivity, and usability, all of which contribute to more effective and engaging learning. However, successful implementation of DER requires consideration of requirements and challenges, as well as learner readiness and infrastructure. Research and further development in this area play an important role in achieving high quality education and preparing students for the demands of today's information society.

References

1. Casey, H. Definitions of digital resources in education. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems* 36(3), - 2008 - 229-248.
2. Clark, R. E. Evidence for confounding factors in research on computer-based instruction. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 33(4) – 1985 - 29-37.
3. Grigoriev S.G., Grinshkun V.V., Krasnova G.A. Recommendations for the effective formation of information resources of educational portals // *Internet portals: content and technology*. Vol. 3. M.: Prosveshcheniye. - 2005 - p. 134-166.
4. Juan, A., & Coleman, J. A. Understanding digital educational resources: Definitions, challenges, and opportunities. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 68(1) – 2020 - 357-376.
5. McKenna, R. A., & Fitzpatrick, R. M. *Multi-media and hypermedia in the college curriculum: A survey and resource guide*. Greenwood Publishing Group -1994
6. Nurgalieva G.K., Artykbaeva E.V. E-learning as a condition for innovative development of the education system. *Bulletin of KazNU. Series of Pedagogical Sciences*. № 1 (35) - 2012
7. Selwyn, N., & Mishra, P. What is digital literacy? A pragmatic investigation. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 29(3), 325-337. 1C. (2010) *DER Development Environment. User's Guide*. 1C Publishing, Moscow- 2006